

Study of Photochromism in Benzenesulphonylhydrazones

M. S. M. RAWAT* and S. MAL**

Department of Chemistry, University of Garhwal, Srinagar-246 174

Manuscript received 22 November 1986, revised 3 June 1986, accepted 22 April 1987

Photochromic behaviour of benzenesulphonylhydrazone derivatives has been investigated in crystalline state, ethanol-ether (2 : 1) and PMMA matrix at liquid air temperature (-180°). Benzenesulphonylhydrazones containing *ortho*-hydroxy group in the aldehydic ring showed reversible colour change on irradiation (365 nm) in solid state and rigid matrices in liquid air temperature. Whereas the presence of electron-withdrawing groups at C_6 -position in the salicylidene ring affected the formation of photo-coloured product. Hydrazones of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde did not show photochromic change and irreversible spectra were obtained on irradiation of their methanolic solution at room temperature.

HYDRAZONES are reported¹ to be photochromic in solid state due to the tautomeric shift. Photochromic studies on quinolyhydrazones² and sulphonylhydrazones of salicylaldehyde³ showed that the presence of *ortho*-hydroxyl group is an essential structural feature for photochromism. In the present study, different types of benzenesulphonylhydrazones of salicylaldehydes and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde are synthesised in order to investigate their photochromic behaviour at liquid air temperature in rigid glassy matrices.

Experimental

Benzenesulphonylhydrazine, *p*-toluenesulphonylhydrazine and *o*-nitrobenzenesulphonylhydrazine were prepared⁴⁻⁶. The required hydrazones (Table 1) were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities (0.01 mol) of each benzenesulphonylhydrazines and salicylaldehydes in dry ethanol (50 ml) for 2-3 h. The hydrazones separated out on concentrating and cooling, which were filtered and purified by repeated crystallisation from methanol (except 1i and 1j, which were crystallised from acetone-hexane solution). Melting points were taken in capillary in H_2SO_4 -bath and are uncorrected.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 580 B and Pye- Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometers. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a Jeol JNM-FX 100 instrument and chemical shifts in δ ppm, referred to TMS. A Pye- Unicam SP 700 spectrophotometer was used for uv-vis measurements. For low temperature experiments, the cell was placed in contact with a thick copper block both placed inside the Dewar flask provided with two quartz optical windows. The procedure of irradiation was similar to those reported earlier¹⁰. The hydrazones are mostly insoluble in non-polar solvents, so ethanol-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Hydrazones*	X	Y	Z	Colour	M p. °C
1a	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	H	Colourless	193 ^a
1b	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	OH	H	Colourless	165 ^a
1c	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	OH	OH	Colourless	167-8
1d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	OH	Br	Colourless	194
1e	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	OH	NO ₂	Light yellow	190-2
1f	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	NO ₂	H	Yellow	154-6
1g	H	OH	CH ₃	Colourless	155
1h	H	NO ₂	H	Light yellow	149
1i	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	OH	H	Yellow	180d
1j	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	NO ₂	H	Yellow	193d

* C, H and N analysis values were within $\pm 0.8\%$ of theoretical values. ^aRef 9.

ether (2 : 1) rigid glassy medium was used¹¹ for the study at liquid air temperature.

PMMA matrix: The following general procedure was adopted for the preparation of PMMA films. The compound was taken in MMA (20 ml; dry and purified) to get approximately 10^{-2} - 10^{-3} M solution. Initiator α, α' -azodiisobutyronitrile (AIBN) (0.001%, w/w) was added and the solution was allowed to polymerise on a water-bath at 70-80° till a viscous solution was obtained (7-8 h). It was then poured into a tube (4 cm dia) up to a fixed mark and allowed to form the film at 40° protected from moisture and light. A piece of the film of uniform thickness (0.15 cm approx.), was used for recording the absorption spectra at 320-600 nm. Thickness of the films was measured by a Essdiel thickness gauge (Shirley Dev. Ltd., U.K.).

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra of benzenesulphonylhydrazones of salicylaldehydes showed the lowering of ν_{C-N} from 1630 to 1620 cm^{-1} and a broad band around 2900 cm^{-1} due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding

** Chemistry Section, O.N.G.C. (B.O.P.), Vasudhara Bhawan, Bombay-400 051.

TABLE 2—ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA OF BENZENESULPHONYLHYDRAZONES

Compd. no.	Concentration employed $M \times 10^{-4}$	Ethanol (at room temp.) λ_{max} (log ϵ) nm	Eth : Ether	Eth : Ether	Eth : Ether
			(before irradiation at room temp.) λ_{max} , nm (log ϵ) (280–600 nm)	(before irradiation) at LAT λ_{max} , nm (log ϵ) (280–600 nm)	(after irradiation) at LAT λ_{max} , nm (log ϵ) (280–600 nm)*
1a	6.3	275(4.86), 380(3.88)	380(3.77)	380(4.04)	N.C.
1b	4.8	276(4.98), 320(4.08)	320(4.13)	320(4.27)	320(4.25), 475(3.89)
1c	5.2	278(4.13), 330(3.95)	327(3.95)	330(4.14)	329(4.13), 475(3.30)
1d	6.2	276(4.07), 333(3.84)	333(3.83)	333(4.17)	N.C.
1e	4.7	285(4.25), 310(4.30), 400(3.57)	310(4.24), 400(3.88)	315(4.26), 400(3.84), 450(3.43)	315(4.25), 400(3.84), 450(3.39)
1f	5.0	264(3.95), 329(3.80)	263(3.94), 329(3.38)	263(4.13), 329(3.83)	I.S.
1g	5.5	278(4.17), 326(3.95)	329(4.0)	329(4.20)	4.75(3.55), 329(4.17)
1h	4.0	265(4.07), 290(4.04), 325(3.66)	290(sh), 330(3.69)	325(4.07)	I.S.
1i	4.4	275(4.0), 322(3.89), 365(3.30)	325(3.90), 365(3.34)	325(4.25), 365(3.77)	325(4.24), 365(3.79), 475(3.63)
1j	4.5	265(3.82), 330(3.30)	265(3.84), 330(3.86)	330(3.87)	I.S.

No correction was made to the spectra for the contraction of the solution on cooling. * N.C. = No change observed in absorption spectra after irradiation at LAT; I.S. = Irreversible spectra were obtained after irradiation, no. of λ_{max} differ with the time of irradiation.

between *o*-OH and imine-N. Absorption frequency obtained around 1 170 and 1 350 cm^{-1} are due to ν_{SO_2} . Strong absorption around 835 cm^{-1} is due to the OH out-of-plane angle bending.

Tosylhydrazones of salicylaldehyde (1b), 5-methylsalicylaldehyde (1c), benzenesulphonylhydrazone of 5-methylsalicylaldehyde (1g) and *o*-nitrobenzenesulphonylhydrazone of salicylaldehyde (1i), showed colour change (colourless/yellow to red) on irradiation (365 nm) in solid state, rigid glassy solvent system (ethanol : ether, 2 : 1) and PMMA films at -180° (liquid air temp.). The red colour faded when the crystalline samples and PMMA films warmed up and the rigid solution softened or illuminated with visible light. Colour change or luminescence is not observed on irradiation at room temperature. Characteristic absorption band near 480 nm appeared in the absorption spectra of these compounds at -180° in rigid glassy solvents and PMMA films. It can be attributed to the intramolecular hydrogen transfer of the phenolic proton to the imine nitrogen followed by *cis*→*trans* isomerisation. A new band near 450 nm appeared in the case of 1e and not in 1d on cooling to -180° in rigid matrices which may be due to the more electronegative nitro group in the previous case than the bromo group in the second case at C_5 -position of the salicylidene ring. The electronegative groups shifted the phenolic proton closer to the imine nitrogen resulting in the increase of *cis*-keto character. These compounds instead of changing into *trans*-keto photoproduct on irradiation (365 nm) showed greenish yellow fluorescence (*cis*-keto*→*cis*-keto) and thus making them photolytically inactive.

Further, ^1H nmr spectra of the hydrazones (1b–1e) showed phenolic protons at δ 12.47, 12.22, 12.65 and 13.78, respectively. In 1c, C_5 -methyl group shielded the phenolic proton, while in 1d and 1e it was deshielded by C_5 -bromo and nitro groups

as compared to 1b and 1c. It indicates the strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding in 1d and 1e.

Compound 1e showed an absorption band around 400 nm in ethanol and ethanol–ether (polar solvents) at room temperature which can be attributed to the transfer of proton from the solute to solvents (II), due to the electron-withdrawing nature of nitro group^{1a}.

Hydrazones of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde 1f, 1h and 1j have not shown photochromic bands at room temperature and liquid air temperature in rigid matrices but showed irreversible changes in the absorption spectra on irradiation for 20–30 min. It can be said due to the degradation of the compounds on irradiation, because nitro compounds which contain in a position *ortho* the nitro group,

I

II

(transition state)

a CH group, are light sensitive¹⁸. Irradiated samples of the compounds gave more than two spots on tlc which vary with the time of irradiation. It may be concluded that the presence of *ortho*-hydroxyl group is an essential requirement for photochromic activity and the substituents present in the benzenesulphonyl ring did not have significant effect while substituents in the salicylidene ring can influence the photochromic behaviour. The photochromic phenomenon of benzenesulphonylhydrazones may have occurred through, enol imine III(a) $\xrightarrow{h\nu}$ enol imine* (excited state) $\rightarrow$ cis-keto amine* (excited state, III(b)) $\rightarrow$ (intermediate) $\rightarrow$ trans-keto amine (photoproduct, III(c)), as suggested by

Nakagaki *et al.*¹⁴, in the case of *N*-salicylideneanilines.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.S.M.R.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for awarding Teacher Fellowship and also to Dr. J. L. Norula, Chemistry Department, for helpful discussions and facility.

References

1. O. V. GHEORGHIU, *Rev. Stint V. Adamachi*, 1946, **32**, 141 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1948, **42**, 1239).
2. J. L. WONG and F. N. BRUSCATO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, 4593.
3. E. HADJOUDIS and D. G. HADJOUDIS, *Chim. Chronica, New Series*, 1975, **4**, 51.
4. H. T. CLARKE, G. S. BABCOCK and T. F. MURRAY, *Org. Synth. Collect.*, 1941, **1**, 85.
5. T. OVRTIUS and F. LORENZEN, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1898, **58**, 166.
6. L. FRIEDMAN, R. L. LITTLE and W. R. REICHEL, *Org. Synth. Collect.*, 1973, **5**, 1055.
7. M. T. BOGERT and A. STUILL, *Org. Synth. Collect.*, 1941, **1**, 220.
8. E. WERTHEIM, *Org. Synth. Collect.*, 1961, **2**, 471.
9. H. ZIMMER, B. H. GROSS, E. H. GERLACK, K. FRY, A. C. PRONAY and H. SCHMANK, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 1667.
10. S. MAL, J. L. NORULA and M. S. M. RAWAT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 120.
11. H. GREENSPAN and E. FISCHER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 2466.
12. M. D. COHEN, G. M. J. SCHMIDT and S. FLAVIAN, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1967, 817.
13. F. SACHS and S. HILPERT, *Chem. Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 3425.
14. R. NAKAGAKI, T. KOBAYASHI, J. NAKAMURA and S. NAGAPURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1977, **50**, 1909.